

First industrial scale mass balance data for the reengineered pedersen process developed within the EU funded project ENSUREAL

David KONLECHNER¹, Michail VAFEIAS², Danai MARINOS², James MWASE³

¹ KON Chemical Solutions e.U., Obermuellnerstrasse 2A, 1020 Vienna, Austria

² Laboratory of Metallurgy, NTUA (National Technical University of Athens), Athens, Greece

³ Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, NTNU (Norwegian University of Science and Technology), Trondheim, Norway

david.konlechner@kon-chem.com

Abstract

Within the following paper, a first mass balance for the revamped industrial Pedersen Process is presented. The target capacity is an alumina output of 500,000 t per year, which is considered a comparable volume to the Bayer Process. The model was carried out using the commercially available HSC software tool from Outotec and consists of three main parts: smelter, hydromet and calcination. Special focus is given to the hydromet section. The volumes that must be handled within the hydromet part are in the range of several thousand cubic meters per hour and therefore will have a significant impact on the footprint of the industrial plant. A solid mass balance model of the Pedersen Process is a valuable tool for ongoing and future optimization of the new industrial-scale Pedersen process within the ENSUREAL project.

Introduction

Developed during the 1920s, the Pedersen Process is a method for alumina (Al_2O_3) production and an alternative to the state-of-the-art Bayer Process. The Pedersen Process uses an electric arc furnace to smelt the raw material containing aluminium and iron with lime and coke. The smelting process separates pig iron and generates a specific synthetic calcium-aluminium slag which is leachable during the further processing. Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) is used to leach the slag, which is then regenerated in a second step through precipitation of alumina (Al_2O_3) by CO_2 . This process has been well described in previous literature. The basic process is shown in a flow diagram in Figure 1¹⁻⁵.

Figure 1. A schematic of the Pedersen Process for alumina extraction¹

Mass and energy balance

The main purpose of the mass and energy balance model is to transfer a chemical process investigated in the lab into an industrial-scale process. The model allows to visualize process-internal reuse of material streams and the effects related to this, e.g. accumulation of trace elements. First data regarding the handled volumes and required energy amounts are generated. This preliminary information is used to develop technical solutions for different scale-up aspects including material storage, material transfer, cooling, and solid-liquid separation. The mass balance is also the first step to estimate the required surface for an industrial plant using the Pedersen Process.

We used the commercially available software tool HSC Chemistry from Outotec to conduct the first industrial scale mass balance for the reengineered Pedersen Process. This tool allows us to generate a flexible balance model for the process. The concept of this model is based on several calculation levels as shown in Figure 2. The scale-up of the Pederson Process steps smelting and calcination are in the working scope of other ENSUREAL project partners. The executed mass balance model considers those two process steps as black boxes that simply execute the chemical processes of slag preparation and alumina production. Blue Metals and Outotec as responsible ENSUREAL project partners will supply detailed data for the up-scaling process and fine tuning of the mass balance. The hydromet section summarizes the blocks from leaching to precipitation Figure 1. This section is balanced in the model in detail. The process streams are calculated at a high level that allows preliminary technology and design decisions for the equipment.

Figure 2 shows the three levels of the mass balance model. Numbers in brackets refer to the blocks shown in Figure 2. Level 1 shows the three main sections of the Pedersen process: smelter, hydromet, and calciner. All input streams are shown as green dash-dotted lines emanating from the TOP (Take Over Point). Output streams are shown as blue dashed lines which transfer products and off gases to the TOP of the plant. Internal process streams are shown as black lines. The slag composition produced in the smelter step (1) is calculated from chemical data. For the inputs and outputs, a direct backchecking of the streams is implemented. The

alumina production in the calciner step (3) is also calculated on a low level of details. The alumina mass flow is linked with the input streams, indicating that the reducing agent or lime also will be converted to the final product. The hydromet part (2) internally calculates the TOP streams for this section and sends data to the lower levels; in addition, it receives data from the lower levels. The general law that input and output must be the same always has to be fulfilled. For example, the input water amount is defined by the moisture of the grey mud and the alumina hydroxide.

Level 2 is focused on the hydromet part (2) of the Pedersen Process. Within the digestion step (21), the different slag phases are dissolved following the chemical reactions below. The leaching yield for each reaction can be defined separately.

Adding CO₂ at the precipitation stage (22) to the solution leads to the formation of solid alumina hydroxide (Al(OH)₃) and the neutralisation of free sodium hydroxide following the chemical reactions below. The efficiency of these two reactions is iterated automatically to meet a closed balance considering also the NaOH and NaAl(OH)₄ loss via the grey mud stream and the alumina hydroxide. In the currently investigated cases, it is nearly 100%.

The digestion / precipitation circuit is shown with thick red lines due to its importance and volume within the hydromet section. The remaining internal process streams at Level 2 are shown as orange lines. Other streams already mentioned at Level 1 are drawn using the same method as before. See Level 3 for a detailed explanation of Level 2 Al(OH)₃ washing (23) and GM washing (24).

Figure 2: Concept of the HSC mass and energy balance with a focus on the hydromet section

Level 3: At this level, the balance of the digestion step (2101-2110), Al(OH)₃ washing (2301-2310) and GM washing (2401-2410) meets the equipment level. The counter current operating system can run ten stages, that each can be

separately switched on and off within the model. For the digestion, the total leaching efficiency is a set value that will be automatically distributed over the active stages. For example, 85% leaching efficiency at three stages results in efficiency of 46.87% per stage. By modifying the model, it is also possible to define the efficiency separately for each stage. Additional parameters to define include the water content of the slurry transferred between the stages and the process temperature.

For the washing models, an ideal reactor concept and full mixing is assumed. The counter current transfer of wash water and the solid phase produces an increase in the chemical elements in the wash water. The reduction of soluble utilities in the solid phase takes place in a similar process. The number of washing stages and the amount of moisture transfers with the solid phase between the stages defines the efficiency and the final loss of reactants.

First results from the balance

The raw materials bauxite, coke and lime are used to produce a within the Pedersen Process leachable slag. The chemical composition of the three input materials used for the pilot tests in Trondheim (D_2.1 table3.1) are summarized in Table 1.

Table 2. Smelter feed streams

(wt%)	Bauxite	Coke	Lime
Al ₂ O ₃	62.00	2.79	0.24
Fe ₂ O ₃	17.00	0.86	0.83
SiO ₂	2.30	5.60	0.46
CaO			95.50
CaCO ₃	1.80		
TiO ₂	2.50		
C		87.68	
LOI / H ₂ O	14.40	3.07	2.97

The preferred Mayenite-phase 12CaO*7Al₂O₃ has a mass distribution of 48wt% CaO and 52wt% Al₂O₃. For the current balance, a composition similar to Experiment 2 generated slag 7 is used. The chemical analysis is summarized in Table 2. Based on the data in Table 2, a first slag phase distribution is also estimated.

Table 3. Chemical analysis D2.1 Experiment 2 Slag 7

(wt%)	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Sum.
Ex.2 Slag 7	45.12	50.54	0.97	0.38	0.02	0.06	1.60	1.30	99.99

Slag phase preliminary assumption based on Al, Ca and Si:

- CA CaO*Al₂O₃ 0.87%
- C3A 3CaO*Al₂O₃ 15.00%
- C12A7 12CaO*7Al₂O₃ 80.00%
- C2Si 2CaO*SiO₂ 4.13%

The design capacity within the project for the industrial scale alumina plant using the Pedersen Process is 500,000 t per year of alumina. The mass balance calculates the required input stream volumes to reach this production capacity. The mass balance is a very useful tool to identify how different decisions affect the overall process streams. In addition, the mass balance provides a first concept of the process for later industrial equipment decisions. Within the model, each stream is defined in much more detail; Figure 3 and Figure 4 present a first impression of the process streams that must be handled within a 500,000 t Pedersen Process.

Figure 3. Mass streams of Level 1 transferred to a Sankey diagram

Figure 4. Mass streams of Level 2 transferred to a Sankey diagram

The following intermediate assumptions are input values to calculate the above given data. These data reflect the current development status of the ENSUREAL project:

- Ore and slag composition as already shown in Table 1 and Table 2
- The limestone has 95.5wt% CaCO_3
- The coke has 87.8wt% C
- The three-stage counter current digestion is carried out at 95 °C with a total leaching yield of 85% for each phase and a water content at the TOP between the stages of 65/65/15wt%
- The process has a saturated leaching solution with ~32g/l NaOH; ~81g/l NaAl(OH)_4 and ~51g/l Na_2CO_3 at a density (95 °C) of 1,09t/m³
- The precipitation of Al(OH)_2 with CO_2 is assumed at a temperature level of 40 °C
- The process has a regenerated solution with ~5g/l NaOH; ~0,1g/l NaAl(OH)_4 and ~129g/l Na_2CO_3 at a density (40 °C) of 1,12t/m³
- The precipitation efficiency is assumed with a yield of >99% and the water content at the TOP to the washing is 20wt%
- Three-stage counter current Al(OH)_3 washing having a water content at the TOP between the stages of 65/65/15wt%
- The five-stage counter current grey mud washing has a water content at the TOP between the stages of 65/65/65/65/30wt%

The 110t/h Al(OH)_3 with 15% water as output stream of the hydromet section of the balance model is equal to approximately 61t/h of Al_2O_3 after calcination. Assuming an availability of the industrial scale Pedersen Process plant of approx. 8200h per year leads to the target capacity of 500,000t Al_2O_3 per year.

The Sankey diagram shows that the $\text{NaAl(OH)}_4/\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3$ circle has the largest volume flow within the system. This circuit will therefore have the biggest impact on the process equipment; for this reason, the equipment must be chosen carefully. In addition, the current numbers assume an average production rate in tons within one hour. The final retention time for each chemical process step will also have a significant impact on the volumes that will be handled as well as the equipment design.

In addition to monitoring the CAPEX of the process, it is even more important to consider the OPEX of a real-life future plant. The CAPEX is an one-time investment,

but design decisions that generate a high OPEX will affect the business during the entire lifetime of the plant. A solid mass and energy balance model allows to reach an optimised CAPEX and OPEX. It is essential to have this data for the further up-scaling procedure of the Pedersen Process

Summary and Outlook

The mass balance shown here is a tool that can be used at a very early stage in a project. The simple, fast and economic investigation of different cases in the mass and energy balance model is already used to have an optimized test program at laboratory scale. The mass balance can be used to make decisions regarding promising strategies that require confirmation or less promising strategies that can be eliminated.

The mass balance is used within the ENSUREAL projects as an important tool to calculate and specify input and output parameters for the required process equipment. Based on this data, first discussion with possible equipment suppliers as well as CAPEX/OPEX investigations starts.

In addition, the Balance is an important tool for supervising pilot tests within the ENSUREAL project. Optimisation can be achieved using direct backchecking of real-life data with the balance and vice versa.

References

1. A. Lazou, C. van der Eijk, E. Balomenos, L. Kolbeinsen and J. Safarian, "On the Direct Reduction Phenomena of Bauxite Ore Using H₂ Gas in a Fixed Bed Reactor", *Journal of Sustainable Metallurgy*, Springer, 2020.
2. F. Azof, *Pyrometallurgical and Hydrometallurgical Treatment of Calcium Aluminate-containing Slags for Alumina recovery*, PhD Thesis, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway;2020
3. M. Vafeias, D. Marinos, D. Pantias, J. Safarian, C. van der Eijk, I. Solheim, E. Balomenos, M. Ksiazek, P. Davris, in *Proceeding of the 2nd International Bauxite Residue Valorisation and Best Practices Conference (BR2018)*, Edited by Y. Pontikes KU Leuven, Athens, Greece, 2018.
4. H. E. Blake, O. C. Fursman, A. D. Fugate, L. H. Banning, "Adaptation of the Pedersen Process to the Ferruginous Bauxites of the Pacific Northwest", *Report of Investigations 6939*, Bureau of Mines, United States Department of the Interior, USA, 1967
5. M. R. Thompson, H. M. McLeod, M. L. Skow, "Recovery of Alumina from Submarginal Bauxites", *Report of Investigations 4528*, Bureau of Mines, United States Department of the Interior, USA, 1949